

Academic
Data Science
Alliance

Five Years of Responsible Data Science

2019 - 2024

5-Year Report and Strategic Plan

ADSA Governance

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Introduction

The Academic Data Science Alliance (ADSA) is a nationally recognized professional association for data science and AI in academia. Founded in 2019 with generous funding from the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation and the Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, ADSA aims to foster a supportive community for sharing new approaches and best practices across academic institutions of all types, from R1 universities to small colleges and Minority-Serving Institutions, as well as like-minded organizations outside academia.

Our Membership program for data science institutions, launched in 2021 with 44 member institutions, has grown to 67 members in FY 2024-2025. As of October 2024, we engage with over 1,200 mailing list recipients, 1,600+ Twitter followers, 1,060+ LinkedIn followers, a Slack community of nearly 1,400, and our Data Science Community Newsletter (DSCN) reaches approximately 7,600 inboxes.

“The ADSA community has provided so many rich opportunities, both virtually and in-person, to meet like-minded people from around the country, who are excited and engaged with providing data science education.”

- Rachel Saidi, Montgomery College

Who We Are

Micaela Parker
Founder and Executive Director

Megan Atkinson
Program Associate

Stella Min
Program Manager

Steve Van Tuyl
Program Manager

Veronica Woodlief
Communications Specialist

Who We Serve

ADSA facilitates learning and sharing opportunities for academic institutions to find the “right path” in their unique campus environments. Broadly, ADSA serves three different groups in academia:

Administrators

Faculty and staff leadership of academic data science initiatives and units (e.g., directors, chairs, managing directors, associate deans) are our primary audience.

Educators

Faculty and staff who teach data science, data analytics, or related skills through formal coursework or informal training are part of our community and benefit from our work.

Researchers

Faculty and staff who use data-driven methodologies in their research or who advance the field with foundational research are part of our community and benefit from our work.

What We Do

- ▶ Guide the emergence and evolution of data science initiatives in higher education.
- ▶ Support current and future leaders of data science programs, initiatives, or units in academia.
- ▶ Steer the field of data science to be more diverse, equitable, inclusive, accessible, responsible, ethical, and open.

How We Do It

Events

We organize in-person and virtual events for the exchange of ideas on effective incorporation of data science, and related emerging technologies such as AI, in teaching and research.

Resource Development

We facilitate the community development of new resources for the advancement of data science and AI best practices in academia.

Professional Guidance

We support a community of current and prospective academic data science leaders as they navigate the academic career trajectory and implement programs and approaches at their institutions.

Community Engagement and Collaboration

We build a community for data scientists in higher education to promote awareness of responsible data science and provide a network for sharing research and teaching approaches that align with our values.

Mission, Vision, Values

Mission

ADSA supports the integration of data science and AI in university research, education, and training across disciplines and empowers all data scientists to openly engage with the ethical implications of their work.

Vision

A community of leaders, researchers, and educators who take responsibility for a just, equitable future where data science approaches are thoughtfully applied, in all domains, for the benefit of all.

Values

We are an open and welcoming community.

We bring people and organizations together.

We value the perspective and experiences of our community.

We advocate for the humans in data science.

We promote working responsibly, ethically, and openly.

Commitment to Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion

We actively solicit keynote speakers, panelists, and participants from a diversity of backgrounds and institutions for all of our events.

Since we began inviting keynote speakers in 2020, 6 of 8 have been women; half identified as Black and two identified as Hispanic. Our Student Keynotes have included students from HBCUs and HSIs, including one who was the first in his family to go to college.

We support faculty and staff from Minority Serving Institutions (MSIs) and two-year colleges to attend our events.

To increase the diversity of attendees, we invite faculty from Minority-Serving Institutions (MSIs) and two-year colleges to our meetings, often with full travel support, and solicit sessions highlighting the efforts and successes of these schools. Our 2023 Annual Meeting included attendees from 3 HBCUs, 10 HSIs, 9 AANAPISIs, 4 two-year colleges, and 2 high schools.

We are intentional about the fields and demographics represented by our Program Committees.

To ensure the programming at our meetings reflects the diversity of fields that make up data science (beyond statistics and computer science), we are intentional about both the fields represented by our Program Committees and their demographics. To date, our Program Committees have had a majority of women (60%) and racial diversity (32% non-White). As an example, the diversity of fields represented by our 2023 Program Committees included: Computational Biology, Political Science, Astronomy, Computer Science, Information Sciences, International Relations, Evolutionary Biology, Mathematics, Biochemistry, Economics, Data Science, Africana Studies, and Biomedical Sciences.

ADSA's Beginnings

Since its inception in 2019, ADSA membership has expanded steadily, from 44 member institutions in the 2021-2022 year to 67 in the 2024-2025 year. The diversity of our members has also expanded to include data science schools, programs, and initiatives from across the US, Canada, Europe, and Africa.

2024-2025 ADSA members include:

As ADSA's membership has grown, so too has our capacity to foster impactful collaborations and initiatives within the data science community. Our flagship events - the Data Science Leadership Summit and the ADSA Annual Meeting - serve as vital forums for advancing shared goals, addressing challenges, and inspiring new projects. Held in-person each year (with the exception of 2020-2021 due to the COVID-19 pandemic), these gatherings bring together the data science community to exchange ideas and develop resources. Marking a milestone for ADSA, the inaugural International Leadership Summit will take place at the American University of Paris in May 2025.

Examples of Our Impact

The [Data Science Leadership Summit](#) provides a vital opportunity for leaders to discuss the challenges and strategies involved in launching and managing data science programs. The summits also offer ADSA valuable insights into areas where support is needed. At our inaugural summit, attendees emphasized the lack of ethical training and societal perspectives in data science coursework - a critical gap, given the power of data science and AI and their potential to cause harm without a strong ethical foundation. In response, ADSA convened an interdisciplinary team of social scientists, humanists, and data scientists who spent two years (2020-2022) creating a framework for embedding ethics into data science. The resulting [Data Science Ethos](#) is free and publicly available, exemplifying how ADSA unites the community to build tools for the greater good.

Another recurring concern voiced by our community was the ill-defined career paths and limited incentives for Research Software Engineers (RSEs) and Data Scientists in academia—particularly compared to more lucrative opportunities in industry. The contributions of RSEs and Data Scientists are essential to advancing research, and their role within the academic ecosystem is critical. In Fall 2022, we partnered with the United States Research Software Engineer Association (US-RSE) to host a two-day workshop aimed at establishing best practices for [Hiring, Managing, and Retaining Data Scientists and Research Software Engineers in Academia](#). Since its publication in August 2023, the Career Guidebook has received over 11,000 views and 5,000 downloads.

Our Vision for the Future

In 2024, data science faces increasing tension amid the rapid advancements of AI and foundational models, and many of our constituents need guidance in navigating this space. The enormous amounts of data required to fuel AI are driving a growing demand for data science expertise.

ADSA's greatest strengths lie in the diversity of domains we engage with and the network of strong, engaged leaders, from all types of institutions, that support our mission. These strengths, combined with the opportunities arising from technological progress, uniquely position us to lead in this rapidly evolving landscape.

We envision a just and equitable future where data science and AI are thoughtfully applied across all domains for the benefit of all. While this is an ambitious vision, ADSA is well-positioned to lead the way forward. Our strategic priorities for the next five years, outlined on the following page, are informed by these strengths and opportunities.

We want our community to recognize us as a gathering place for open conversations around the definition and evolution of the field, including the relationship between data science and AI.

A Strategic Plan Toward Our Vision

Over the next five years, our strategic priorities will focus on leveraging our strengths and opportunities, centering our efforts on cultivating mission-aligned partnerships with industry, building a sustainable revenue portfolio with a two-year runway, and expanding our membership program nationally and internationally.

FORTIFY OUR BASE

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- ▶ Boost member enrollment by reaching out to potential members, inviting feedback from current members, and enhancing membership tiers and benefits.
- ▶ Enhance members' experience and engagement by facilitating opportunities for networking, discussion, and collaboration.
- ▶ Reduce barriers to ADSA membership and participation in ADSA events and increase our 2-year college and MSI members.

BROADEN OUR REACH

2

- ▶ Respond to the evolving needs and priorities of academic data science initiatives as new technologies emerge.
- ▶ Increase awareness of ADSA through a broad communications strategy and strategic partnerships across sectors.
- ▶ Expand funding to sustain core operations of ADSA through mission-aligned partnerships and grant-writing.

BUILD OUR LEGACY

3

- ▶ Develop a reputation as the leading professional association for academic data science.
- ▶ Steer the field of data science to be more diverse, equitable, inclusive, accessible, responsible, ethical, and open.
- ▶ Position ADSA as the leading source of career advancement information for data scientists and future leaders of data science initiatives in academia.

